

The Chemistry of Jute-lignin. Part VII.

Behaviour of Organic Compounds towards ClO_2 and its Significance on the Constitution of Lignin.

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Schmidt and co-workers (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 1529) have tried the action of ClO_2 on a number of organic compounds and have found that water-soluble products, mainly aliphatic acids and in many cases chloro-compounds are obtained when a free phenolic group is present. The well known action of ClO_2 on lignin which yielded oxalic acid, carbon dioxide and maleic acid but no aromatic compound, was interpreted as an evidence in favour of the presence of a free phenolic group in lignin. This view was also corroborated by Fuchs and Honsig (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 2850).

The action of diazomethane in introducing one methoxyl group (assuming a molecular weight of 820) in lignin as observed by Freudenberg and Hess (*Annalen*, 1926, 448, 124) as well as by Fuchs and Horn (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1691), was also used as an argument in support of the free phenolic group theory. The facts that cellulose and other polysaccharides behave similarly with diazomethane and that Willstätter-lignin is insoluble in dilute alkalis, compelled Freudenberg to change his views, so that he made no provision for any such phenolic group in his constitutional formula for lignin ("Tannin, Cellulose und Lignin", 1933, 123.)

In view of these facts, it was thought worth while to study the action of ClO_2 on more varied types of organic compounds in order to see if the conclusions drawn from the reactions of Schmidt and others were really justified. As will be seen in Table I, all aromatic bodies with a free phenolic group are very readily attacked; but it has also been found that when these phenolic groups are protected either by methylation or acetylation, the resulting compounds are still susceptible to oxidation by ClO_2 though less readily (Table II). Further aliphatic OH group in the side-chain attached to the benzene ring (*e.g.* benzyl alcohol) is also oxidised by ClO_2 (Table III) but when it is occupied by methoxyl or acetyl group, it is no longer acted upon by ClO_2 . As lignin contains beyond doubt, more than one methoxyl

group attached to the benzene ring, and hydroxyl group attached to the side-chain, it is obvious that the fact that it is acted upon slowly by ClO_2 , cannot in any way prove the existence of any aromatic hydroxyl group in the molecule. The comparative resistance of acetylated or methylated lignin to the action of ClO_2 , may thus be due to the protection of hydroxyl groups in the side-chain.

Substituents like Cl, Br and NO_2 make the phenols comparatively more resistant to the action of ClO_2 and as chloro-, bromo-, and nitro-lignins as well behave in a similar way, it may be inferred that these substituents enter at least partly the benzene ring, when lignin is chlorinated, brominated or nitrated.

It has been observed that the dioxymethylene group in lignin is quite resistant towards ClO_2 . It is, therefore, unlikely that ClO_2 opens up free phenolic group by the removal of the dioxymethylene group from lignin and thus exposing free phenolic groups to be acted upon.

It has been found that when aliphatic hydroxyl groups are methylated or acetylated, they resist the action of ClO_2 . It has also been found that methoxyl or acetyl value of jute, delignified by the ClO_2 method, is due to pectin matter. As these groups in delignified fibre are not acted upon by ClO_2 it may be concluded that pectin is entirely aliphatic in nature, thus corroborating the views of Ehrlich and Sommerfield (*Bio chem. Z.*, 1925, 168, 263). As pectin obtained from jute is perfectly resistant to ClO_2 , it is evidently dissimilar from lignin in structure and hence the author is opposed to the view that lignin owes its origin to pectin.

It has further been observed that small amounts of chlorolignin are invariably formed when ClO_2 acts on lignin. The amount of chlorolignin formed by the action of ClO_2 gas is considerably less than that formed by ClO_2 solution. This is probably the reason why sodium sulphite or acetic acid, both excellent solvents for chlorolignin, had to be used in Schmidt's process of delignification, while thorough washing with water is generally sufficient if ClO_2 in gaseous form is used for the purpose. This chlorolignin is evidently responsible for the slight yellow colour of the delignified fibre. As the chlorolignin resists the action of ClO_2 and of 42% HCl, it has often been mistaken for lignin. The chloro-lignin has actually been isolated and analysed as regards its solubility, chlorine-content, methoxyl etc. and found to be almost identical with that obtained in the usual way with chlorine.

Incidentally it may be remarked that HCl-lignin, obtained from teak-wood (by 42% HCl), takes a much longer time to dissolve when gaseous ClO_2 is passed through its aqueous suspension and leaves behind more residue of chloro-lignin than lignin from jute; this fact supports the view of the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 263) that jute-lignin is less highly polymerised than wood-lignins.

EXPERIMENTAL.

ClO_2 was prepared by warming on the water-bath (35° - 40°) an intimate mixture of chemically pure oxalic acid (20 g.) and potassium chlorate (25 g.) with 80 c.c. of dilute sulphuric acid (100 c.c. of sulphuric acid diluted to 325 c.c.) in a round bottomed flask fitted with all glass connections and absorbing the gas in a series of gas-washers containing water. These were collected and made to a litre and 5 c.c. of it were diluted with 20 c.c. of water and titrated with $N/10$ -thio-sulphate after adding 3 c.c. of $2N$ -potassium iodide solution, and 10 c.c. of N -sulphuric acid in the usual way. The original solution was diluted with water so as to be approximately $0.25N$. The solution was preserved in a bottle wrapped with black paper and fitted with a well ground stopper. The strength remains practically unchanged when kept in a cool place provided the stopper is made gas-tight with vaseline.

About 0.5 g. of the substance (pulverised if solid) was taken in an Erlenmeyer flask with a good stopper, 10 c.c. of the ClO_2 solution were added and the stopper closed immediately. It was kept in a dark cool place and shaken mildly from time to time. After several hours (12-48) the solution was titrated with thiosulphate as described above, after adding 20 c.c. of cold water. Duplicate experiments were always done and the mean value for thiosulphate was accepted. The strength of ClO_2 was determined every time before exposure and also after the same period in a blank experiment in a similar flask, the mean being taken as the original titre. The difference was always found to be quite negligible (0.1—0.2 c.c.) and so the complicated arrangement of Schmidt and Graumann (*Ber.*, 1922, 54, 1862) was not adopted. More concordant results were obtained if the flask was cooled to 5° - 10° before the addition of potassium iodide and titration. The experimental results are given in Table I, II and III below.

TABLE I.
 Room temp. = 22°—25°

Substance.	Time.	Original titre (thio.)	Final titre. (thio.)	Substance.	Time.	Original titre (thio.)	Final titre.
Phenol	12 hrs.	21.50 c.c.	3.10 c.c.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	46 hrs.	21.20 c.c.	2.20 c.c.
Resorcinol	"	"	0.0	Guaiacol	"	"	1.10
Catechol	"	"	"	Eugenol	"	"	0.50
Hydroquinone	"	"	30.1	<i>iso</i> Eugenol	"	"	1.0
<i>m</i> -Cresol	24	21.35	1.80	<i>cyclo</i> Hexanol	"	21.00	1.80
<i>p</i> -Cresol	"	"	0.15	Orcinol	40	"	0.10
Salicylic acid	"	"	0.50	Protocatechuic acid	"	"	0.30
Vanillin	"	"	2.15	Pyrogallol	"	"	0.0
Vanillic acid	"	"	4.30	Phloroglucinol	48	20.90	0.0
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	48	21.20	0.20	Gallic acid	"	"	0.05

By taking equimolecular proportions of the phenolic compounds and exposing them to the action of ClO_2 for the same time and at the same temperature, it has been found that the greater the number of the free hydroxyl groups, the more readily it is decomposed. The results are not shown here as it has no direct bearing on the constitution of lignin.

 TABLE II.
 Room temp. = 21—23°.

Compound.	Time.	Original titre (thio.)	Final titre (thio.)	Compound.	Time.	Original titre (thio.)	Final titre in (thio.)
Anisol	24 hrs.	20.35 c.c.	10.20 c.c.	Acetyl salicylic acid	36 hrs.	20.0 c.c.	13.7 c.c.
Phenetol	"	"	15.45	Vanillic acid	"	"	10.50
Phenyl acetate	36	"	12.75	dimethyl ether	"	"	"
Resorcinol di-methyl ether	48	20.25	6.90	<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzoic acid	40	"	7.65
Catechol di-methyl ether	"	20.20	8.70	<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzoic acid	"	"	7.80
Hydroquinone dimethyl ether	"	"	7.70	<i>cyclo</i> Hexanol methyl ether	45	19.50	12.0
<i>m</i> -Cresol methyl ether	46	"	9.50	Phloroglucinol trimethyl ether	"	"	9.75
<i>p</i> -Cresol methyl ether	"	"	8.90	Pyrogallol trimethyl ether	"	"	8.70
Salicylic acid methyl ether	"	"	8.85	Benzoquinone	32	"	40.0
				Acetophenone	"	"	19.00

TABLE III.

Room temp. = 20—24°.

Substance.	Time.	Original titre (thio).	Final titre (thio).	Substance.	Time.	Original titre (thio).	Final titre (thio).
Benzene	48 hrs.	21.50 c.c.	21.25 c.c.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenol	24 hrs.	19.90 c.c.	9.0 c.c.
<i>cyclo</i> Hexane	"	"	21.30	Phthalic acid	48	21.50	21.30
Toluene	"	"	10.80	Cinnamic acid	"	21.0	19.90
<i>p</i> -Xylene	"	"	8.0	Furfural	"	"	nil
<i>o</i> -Xylene	"	"	7.0	Pyromucic acid	"	"	nil
Benzoic acid	"	"	21.25	Methylated lignin (34.41% OMe)	"	19.90	8.90
Benzaldehyde	"	"	0.30	Acetylated lignin (33.32% acetic acid)	48	"	11.0
Mandelic acid	45	20.90	14.90	Pectin from jute	36	19.5	18.90
Benzyl alcohol	"	"	Nil	Cellulose triacetate	36	19.50	19.10
Piperonal	48	"	9.80	Ethyl acetate	24	"	18.70
Piperonylic acid	"	"	20.80	Cellulose octaacetate	48	19.90	19.75
Safrol	"	20.50	2.20	Ethyl alcohol	"	"	18.50
<i>iso</i> Safrol	"	"	1.25	Diethyl ether	"	"	19.65
Trinitrophenol	"	20.80	15.80	Phenyl acetic acid	"	21.50	21.0
Nitrolignin	36	"	8.0	Tribromophenol	"	"	10.20
Trichlorophenol	"	19.90	9.0	Bromolignin	"	"	8.75
Chlorolignin (25.8% Cl)	"	"	8.75				
Lignin (by 42% HCl at 20°)	"	"	Nil				
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	30	"	6.85				

It will be seen from above that hydroaromatic compounds behave just like the aromatic. Also, the only substituent in the benzene ring which does not make it unstable towards ClO_2 is the carboxyl; side-chains are ultimately oxidised to benzoic acid as usual. The behaviour of quinone and hydroquinone is difficult to explain, as the final titre is greater than the original. All double bonds are not unstable, cinnamic acid is stable but not safrol. Furan compounds are very easily decomposed by ClO_2 .

SUMMARY.

1. Action of ClO_2 on a large number of organic compounds has been tried and it has been found that all phenolic compounds are readily oxidised by it.

2. Methylated or acetylated phenolic compounds are comparatively more stable towards ClO_2 but not resistant.

3. As lignin contains more than one methoxyl group attached to the benzene ring, the action of ClO_2 on it cannot prove the presence of free phenolic OH in the molecule.

4. Substitutents like Cl, Br or NO_2 make the phenols comparatively more resistant to ClO_2 and as chlorolignin, bromolignin and nitrolignin behave similarly, it is inferred that these enter at least partly the benzene ring in lignin.

5. From the behaviour of methylated or acetylated aliphatic compounds and also that of delignified jute it is concluded that pectin in jute is aliphatic in nature.

6. During delignification, a slow side-reaction takes place with the formation of chlorolignin which has been isolated and examined.

7. The dioxymethylene group is stable towards ClO_2 as also the carboxyl attached directly to the ring. Side-chains are oxidised to carboxylic acids as usual.

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